

FAIRplus Sustainability White Paper

“FAIR is for life, not just for Christmas!!”

Authors

Name	Affiliation
Bryn Williams-Jones	Open PHACTS Foundation
Nick Lynch	Open PHACTS Foundation & Curlew Research

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Abstract

IMI, other research funders and the commercial Life Science industry (e.g. EFPIA companies) have invested significantly in projects over the years. The data that is generated in these projects are often not accessible nor findable let alone reusable beyond the original scientist or project. This has involved a huge waste of effort and money for research funders that needs to be addressed to ensure that science can meet future societal challenges with speed and quality of data, feeding AI/ML workflows with machine readable data. FAIRification of data is considered a route to reduce these issues with data access and reuse and to enhance the longer term value of previously generated project data.

The FAIR principles have gathered significant momentum reaching all aspects of Health & Life Sciences and beyond, but the practical implementation of FAIR takes time, effort and longer term commitment. Sustainability of tools, services and resources is critical to support the implementation of FAIR across the breadth of

stakeholders and organisations. Organisations will fall into different maturity levels and have different priorities, and FAIR adoption and the value from the wider data exploitation will take several iterations of these FAIR services and platforms. It is these challenges with FAIR sustainability that this white paper seeks to discuss and suggest options to ensure that FAIR tools and services and the necessary supporting deliverables are not just a buzzword that gained brief management attention. We need to ensure that FAIR approaches support longer term value to the R & D community and for instance have a positive impact on science reproducibility of experiments in the future and decision support and AI/ML that relies on data and its alignment with the key FAIR principles. Equally important will be supporting a new generation of researchers to understand and adopt future FAIR best practices and this will require engagement and support from the wider ecosystem of funders, academia and industry.

What is FAIR and why does it matter?

FAIR¹ may have started as a movement but has been gathering significant momentum over the last seven years since the initial activities at a Lorentz conference and the papers that came from this. The [FAIRplus project](#) was established to support the next steps with FAIR adoption from a practical perspective across IMI projects and its project partners and more about this will be covered through examples in this paper. Importantly, FAIR has always been a global movement, and the initial FAIR activities have spawned a large number of programmes and initiatives that have acronym-based names including FAIR in some form (Carole Goble [FAIRplus 2020 keynote](#); Dunning, Sansone, Teperek. [FAIR coordination layer cake](#)).

There is a large energy and industry around this now, including the recently completed [RDA data maturity model](#) and business models around assessing FAIR and metrics. With this growing list of FAIR resources, [FAIRassist](#)² has been

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <https://fairassist.org/>

developed to help the scientist discover resources to measure and improve FAIRness. One of the key factors in FAIR is its tractability, and the resonance of its simplicity to funders, management and politicians - the fact that this is a non-complex concept over a very complex set of activities is important. In combination with the [EOSC activities](#), the establishment of community [data commons](#) has really driven the agenda to clarify the value of FAIR beyond the fundamentally introspective data expert community. The various data commons activities (e.g. [National Cancer Institute](#), [Australian Research Data Commons](#)) around the globe are important drivers of innovation, but FAIR also applies to digital objects and other assets - software, SOPs and other important resources.

FAIR principles are exactly that, principles and NOT practice. There's no dogma, and implementation can be quite complex as has been observed by many of the FAIR initiatives that have tried to develop and apply FAIR principles. FAIR is essential to enable the flow of information among collaborating yet competing groups with considerable turnover in their membership, and variable project/initiative life spans. Reduction of knowledge loss is the key factor here and time to value for the data enrichment, and has to fit into a complex and competing world of stakeholders; between individual projects, home institutions and companies, funders and differing global standards. Not all the resources and repositories can be fully FAIR - in some cases knowing where the data is (Accessible & Findable [FA]), is more important than whether it is individually interoperable. So FAIR has to be both flexible and context-sensitive, and resources have to be recognised for the FAIR principles that apply, even if they cannot support the full FAIR definition. At the earliest stages of project formation, it is vital to consider FAIR asset sustainability from the legal, financial, communications and outreach, and IT implementation perspectives. Beneficiaries can be separate from the producers of the data, and may not have very direct connections. FAIRification can be considered a contextual approach for instance "FAIR enough" for the intended purpose is the primary driver and supports practical approaches to the FAIRification journey.

Challenges with FAIR adoption

Data sharing and open science has been driving towards FAIR for over a decade, but establishing these principles as the norm is proving to be an extremely slow process. Many of the same old concerns exist, but the top-down and bottom-up drive for open science have difficulty in connecting in a meaningful way at the institutional level which struggle to see the ROI. FAIR is not the same as Open, there are similarities, but many sociological reasons come into play that need a more sophisticated approach - e.g. [GDPR](#) for clinical data. FAIR is not about harmonising all data into one schema, and publishing it in RDF. Interoperability requires a purpose, and a business question to answer. FAIRification is difficult, and expensive, but shouldn't be a blocker to FAIR. FAIR does not mean everyone gets the same, but

everyone gets what they need. Understanding what differing stakeholders need is not simple, and should be prioritised.

Given that the utility and application of FAIRness is very subjective - and depends largely on the business question - there is not, and cannot be, one organisation that assesses and judges FAIRness. FAIRness is, as it were, in the eye of the user-their individual setting drives both what they need to consume, what they use it for, and their own view on the FAIRness of any given resource or data set that they are using for this. In terms of the FAIRplus project, we focus on empowering users to answer their own business questions in the best way that they see fit using the deliverables and best practice from the project. For instance in a large pharma company, this can of course involve their own internal data, data from academic repositories, and data or resources/services from SMEs. Each of these will have their own variable FAIRness, and focus on some or all of the FAIR principles to varying degrees, but have to be assembled together to answer a business question for that large pharma. Given that there are multiple stakeholders, with varying levels of awareness and understanding, implementation of FAIR is non-trivial - and can be further complicated by competing financial incentives. For SMEs, re-implementing part of their internal workflows to enable a customer to build their product into a private internal workflow, the return on investment to be fully FAIR is very tough to justify. This is a theme we will explore in greater detail later in this white paper.

FAIR is more than a set of standards, it implies a step change in the way an organisation considers the value of data, the level of investment needed in generating the data, and the data lifecycle from its birth to its longer term usage and reuse. FAIR is also critical in supporting the larger goals of reproducibility. FAIR is a journey and the change process involved in FAIR adoption needs to be addressed at all levels of an organisation with appropriate stakeholder engagement, collaboration and change management defined along the journey.

Those organisations who are successfully implementing FAIR have the following:

- High level sponsorship (senior leaders)
- Alignment to key organisational goals
- FAIR adoption as part of their digital & data strategy
- Alignment to business value of being more FAIR
- FAIR is the process but it's not overshadowing the 'Why'
- Specific value drivers that FAIR can address in the shorter term (Findable especially)
- Alignment to key business questions that need to be addressed

Interviews on the approach to FAIR

As part of this work we have carried out a range of “Voice of Customer” (VoC) interviews with several organisations, including SMEs & larger pharma including:

- Technology and ontology companies, providing data platforms and services
- Biotechs including AI focused Biotechs
- Larger pharma and their approach to different data sets/types
- Publishers and those with content services
- Data repositories handling core research data

The interviews have shown so far:

- FAIR awareness is variable depending on the organisation type and focus
- FAIR is a great buzzword for management and one that they are familiar with
- SME service and technology organisations are focused on their end product/service
 - their service is tailored by what the customer (data and service consumer) will pay for and value in the short and long term timescale
- FAIR as a mantra is not always top of their priorities as compared to delivering the service or product.
- FAIR is more a side issue really, each and every facet of the FAIR acronym are not always necessary for the data consumers' focus
 - organisations may be following some of the key FAIR principles without being particularly aware of FAIR
 - Interoperability is key for much of data integration use cases and value
 - Chemistry interoperability is essential, and usage of InChI as a means of interoperability between datasets predominates
 - For Biotechs Interoperability is more important than Findability and Accessibility
 - *Context comment: superficially this does not seem logical, if you can't find the data do you really care if it's interoperable? The really reflects that the use case is the real driver of any given customers interest, rather than the FAIR principles per se*
- Larger pharma are focusing FAIRification efforts on higher value datasets in the clinical and real world evidence space, with the emphasis initially on datasets rather than data services
- The value of FAIR will mean different things to different stakeholders, and in some cases can be seen as a 'cost' to producers who may not necessarily themselves benefit from the effort involved - the benefits are largely experienced by the consumers
- The reality remains that subject matter expertise (public and private) largely develop the description of the action and legal agreements in any given project. Whilst this is in and of itself a good thing, in the early consortium

dialogue too little time and effort is spent on sustainability, and the realities of asset definition/management, ROI aspirations, data strategy and re-use plans reduction of legal complexity, realistic financial forecasting for post-project sustain funding, and marketing. Communications of future asset management with respect to to FAIR data is not defined really enough in initial project dialogues. Funding body timelines and application pressure reduces the option to think larger and beyond the funding period. Whilst data management plans are now an accepted part of the project planning process, we need to elevate the importance of FAIR data sustain planning at the earliest possible stage in project planning.

4 points to summarise: Summing up state of FAIR in the interviews

- FAIR awareness is patchy across Life Sciences. We need to be focused on the value not just the acronym
- Many organisations are focusing purely on entity interoperability without worrying about the rest of the indicators at this time as this use case directly impacts their current data workflows.
- Differences across the stakeholders and personas. For those providing platforms there is more interest in FAIR than in the data providers
- We need to be realistic about the FAIR journey and what is in it for each party involved (What's in it for me! (WIIFM))

Learnings from our project Squads during FAIRplus

One area the FAIRplus work packages have been focussing on, is the FAIRification of existing and currently running IMI projects' datasets. In pursuing this work a number of fundamental lessons have been identified that reinforce some of the key aspects detailed across the FAIR adoption workflow.

For IMI projects that have completed and closed and where no data agreement was established as an output from the project, data access is very hard (nigh impossible at times!). It's been hard to set up a data access agreement with projects in this closed state since no one in the project is around to support the engagement and get sign off from the consortium members. This exemplifies the challenges industry and other stakeholders have with retrospective FAIRification where key data consent agreements are needed.

Consequences of GDPR can also have huge implications for data access and some of the best practice in this regard that the project has been collecting has been fed into the Ethics work package outputs. The impact of GDPR regulations also emphasises the importance of [Beacon APIs](#) (e.g. [GA4GH](#)) for making anonymised

health data discoverable for research and clinical purposes. Again these items need to be established during the running of a project for the value of the project's data to be realised.

For ongoing and future projects, the IMI Data Catalogue can play a significant role in the support for FAIR data as projects use this Catalogue for their data assets.

A key outcome and benefit from sustainability will be the ability to make data “FAIR at birth” through usage of the output from FAIRplus and other FAIR groups which will avoid the challenges and costs of retrospective FAIRification. In short, prospective FAIRification is the route forward for all projects (not just public private initiatives such as IMI) for where we want to see full value from the investments in these projects.

Orientation & Situation

What is involved in the FAIR workflow?

In thinking about FAIRness and FAIR in Life Science and health, let us start by aligning this to the data lifecycle and the platforms and services that support this lifecycle. At the far end we have the data consumer, often the Life Science Research organisation (Pharma, Biotech etc. - those with a mission to drive new discoveries) who will be both creating data themselves internally, but more importantly consuming data (external & internal). At the other end will be the data producers and the various stages of data production from the initial scientist in the lab running an experiment to further downstream steps and how this data is collected, aggregated and then published. This final publishing has been the traditional world of the scientific publisher, where a single researcher would publish their paper with associated data in the past. This workflow has expanded with the vision of big data and the businesses seeking to build knowledge bases across larger swathes of the scientific entities and value chain, the final steps of which involve collecting existing data, annotating and enriching and finally publishing.

Figure: Data Lifecycle

Who are the stakeholders in FAIR?

So, in thinking about the stakeholders in FAIR within R&D, we come back to the basics of Data consumers and producers. As discussed further below, for some organisations, they are involved as both data provider and consumers, and this will be typical of a larger research organisation with its own R&D groups creating data at key points along the Life Science value chain.

Equally important in identifying the stakeholders is thinking of the different persona and organisations involved in these steps. We would suggest there are a range of stakeholders in FAIR in the Life Science:

- Larger pharmaceutical & Biotech organisations (both those pursuing experimental science and also those with a strong AI driven focus)
- Research organisations (e.g. non profit, academic, institutional)
- Research funders (foundations, government and state, charities)
- Technology organisations (e.g. informatics tools, data annotation, ontology platforms, AI tools)
- Content providers

- Service providers
- Patient Organisations
- Wider Healthtech ecosystems, see later for discussion on EHR data and Flatiron

In terms of size of organisation, the term SME can cover a huge range of organisations from single person consultancy to a 200 FTE biotech/technology. With this ambiguity of size, we are focusing on the lower end and also on the technology, data content and service provider groups. These SMEs will have their own pressures and drivers compared to established and larger organisations.

FAIR paradox - where does FAIR add value? When is something Fair enough?

There is a paradox in play that at one level, the FAIRness of data is predominantly a benefit to the data consumer. The push to FAIRness does of course simplify data integration and management issues for the data consumer, but FAIRness can similarly be seen as a cost and complication to the producer.

There is of course an argument that the producer will have more 'customers' in the long term, but for SMEs and technical specialists, the benefits are realised almost entirely on the consumer side. The SMEs 'special sauce' is of course very much of interest, but the SME as a 'special sauce producer' does not necessarily have to give much or any thought to how their data integration and management practices fit with those of their consumer. In the consumer mind of course, how they integrate and manage any data they ingest is a business fundamental which can and does influence vendor choices. As in so many things, the uptake of FAIR practices will to an extent be driven by who pays for data FAIRification, and where FAIRified data fits in the current biodata ecosystem. Assigning the value of FAIR data will be one of the key considerations going forward; in the context of Life Science, does FAIR data provide a value-add to the development of new modalities with revenue generation possibilities. As with any commercial business, a Life Science business will make investment decisions on new services and data based on whether they can bring new innovation or bring value quicker by shortening the development cycle.

In the current marketplace, consumers seem very reluctant to pay for data FAIRness, whilst supporting the need for FAIR data as a necessity. For many SMEs, the benefit of FAIR data is difficult to realise, and how it affects their business model is yet to be determined.

Industry Example: FAIR versus manual Curation!

We can take examples from the wider healthcare domain, and where data has long been considered a prime part of an organisation's products or services. Roche [acquired Flatiron Health for \\$2.1B in 2018](#), taking oncology patient outcomes as a significant therapy area and one where stakeholders had long lamented the lack of visibility into real world treatment patterns and outcomes. As fewer than 5% of cancer patients participate in clinical trials, most of what happens to patients in the real world is hidden, trapped in thousands of disparate software systems (EHRs) spanning oncology providers, insurers, payers and labs. Exposing what happens to the other 95% of patients could reveal insights that would help improve future treatment decisions, enable possible new drugs and diagnostics, and ultimately improve outcomes for cancer patients. For instance, the [Flatiron](#) vision was to address this challenge by aggregating patient data from EHRs in community oncology practices across the US, thereby transforming it into a unified and rich dataset. Accomplishing this took a huge investment and required a painstaking process of tech-enabled data extraction, **human curation and annotation** from the EHR systems of hundreds of oncology practices. That investment has paid off for Flatiron in a big way, initially through data licensing contracts with virtually all of the major oncology drug companies, and most recently through the purchase of Flatiron by Roche.

It is easy to focus on the size and complexity of the Flatiron Health deal and its relevance to the FAIR data setting. Some realism should also be employed here in that perhaps the internal incentives within Roche for Flatiron Health were more the value of the 'missing' 95% of patient data, than any necessarily FAIR data driven narrative. As such, the value of any given data set will often offset the complexity of its integration and use. Whilst data FAIRness can greatly simplify downstream activities after such an acquisition, the FAIRness of any given data set may not have any bearing on its value.

Industry Example: The complexity of sustain!

As an illustrative example of the challenges that are faced with sustaining digital assets from outside the IMI world, consider the Pistoia Alliance HELM project. HELM grew out of the need to develop macromolecular nomenclature standards to enable data services commonly used in the small molecule space to be developed and built for biotherapeutics. It is worth noting that HELM was initiated by Pfizer out of their own need to represent biotherapeutics internally and present the structures in a simple way.

- From 2013, the [Pistoia Alliance](#) funded pilots and then a full project that has resulted in a fully certified ISO standard (technical guidance for [ISO 11238 TS](#)

[19844](#)) that has been widely adopted by the industry and also global data repositories such as EMBL-EBI and [NCBI PubChem](#).

- Whilst this is a great story of successful delivery, funding for sustainability and development of the HELM standards has been a continual challenge that has necessitated central Pistoia Alliance funding to support it once the member funded pilot and projects to develop HELM were completed.
- No pharma companies wanted to commit to the funding necessary for sustain and development, even though the HELM standards have had a very significant impact and are a key piece of pharma-relevant data infrastructure.
- Whilst superficially this seems like pharma companies wanting to have their cake and eat it, the reality is that pharma companies exist to discover drugs, not to build globally applicable data infrastructure for the scientific community as a whole.
- For individual pharma companies, the list of projects to sustain grows ever larger (non-discretionary spend), whilst those individuals within companies who engage in these projects change and move to other initiatives or often other companies. Managing a portfolio of collaborative data assets is complex and tough, making it hard to articulate how any one of them contributes directly to the company's own drug portfolio which will always remain their priority for investment.
- The future governance of the HELM standard has been transferred to [IUPAC](#) but the sustainability and funding challenges are not diminished given the breadth of IUPAC's portfolio and funding model. Funding for future HELM enhancements would need to be raised through new initiatives.

Consequently there is a gap in the sustain landscape between valuable collaborative assets which are widely adopted in the community, and a partner who can sustain and develop these assets for the community as a whole in the longer term. Another effect in play is distance from the patient. If we look at examples like [OHDSI](#) and [CDISC](#), there has been a lot of pharma industry funding, impact and development in simplifying healthcare data and clinical interchange standards. These are of course vital parts of the pharma value chain, but their positioning in the translational medicine/biology space is a particularly industry-specific area of activity that has clear impact on clinical trial progression and market access. This has to a very large extent driven the uptake and success of these initiatives, but also highlights the challenge involved in developing and sustaining similar programmes in the preclinical/early research space. Beyond the HELM example detailed above, another pertinent example would be [INCHI](#) standards, used widely across the industry and chemical space, yet perpetually underfunded and sustained by community efforts through IUPAC. Whilst having a key role to play in early pharma R&D, the lack of direct tangible impact on the clinical, regulatory and market access space ensure these initiatives are perpetually tough to justify spending with pharma budget holders. Equally since these have already reached adoption, the options to obtain

future funding are limited in that funding is focussed on new ideas and not often platform sustainability. Similarly, the industry-focussed nature of these resources means that funding through academic routes is similarly tough, complex, and unlikely to succeed.

Sustainability and its importance

As discussed, the implementation of FAIR is often considered a journey and in setting up the FAIRplus work packages, the longer term needs for FAIR were considered critical to success. This includes setting down a framework that will support the key elements needed for implementation impact and longer term value from FAIR activities including both practical deliverables as well options for determining maturity along a FAIR adoption journey.

As part of this longer term impact, the sustainability of the deliverables from FAIRplus were part of the work packages planned and during the early stages of the project the options for sustainability were analysed. A sustain plan for the FAIRplus Cookbook has already been identified through this sustain planning work with the Cookbook being recognised as part of ELIXIR Programme Interoperability Platform. This is a significant step in sustaining the outcomes for the project.

What is a sustainable Asset? & Stakeholders

In the context of sustainability and FAIRPlus, we will define sustainability in the context of some of the deliverables from the project.

WP	Asset	Summary	Contributors	Consumers
2	FAIRplus Cookbook - methods/recipes	Recipes to enable FAIRification of data	Members of FAIRplus consortia including EFPIA and IMI.	Data providers and Data consumers across organisations sizes. Especially those creating data and alignment to Data Management plans.

A key aspect of sustainability is understanding the perspective of both the contributors to the asset, and the consumers of that asset over the longer term. During a project such as FAIRplus, the delivery of an asset will progress through several stages and the balance of contributors versus consumers will differ and evolve over time.

- During the project and prior to release:
 - Contributors will be members of the project (e.g. FAIRplus) weighted in the ratios of EFPIA/IMI colleagues as defined in the WPs and contribution agreements. Plus other experts/SME who have an interest and time available.
 - Release to the wider community before project end
 - Consumption: Little consumption at this point
- Stages of public release of versions
 - Early alpha release
 - Beta release
 - Evolve as needed with additions
 - Emerging Governance process
 - Sustainable release
 - Ability to evolve where needed
 - Usable in its current state

WP	OUTPUT	CURRENT SOLUTION	SUSTAINABILITY	ASSET OWNERS
2	FAIRplus Cookbook - methods/recipes	GitHub repository	Decision: Core part of ELIXIR Programme Interoperability Platform's tasks. Stay on GitHub;	Philippe Rocca-Serra

For an asset to be sustainable it firstly needs to be valuable to the community that it is supporting, evidenced by :

- Clear take up of the asset by the wider community beyond the project
- Value to those using the asset in its current state/version
- A mechanism & process to allow continued contributions from outside the project
- A mechanism & process to allow continued contributions after the FAIRplus project concludes
- A welcoming environment to support those contributing
- Clear Product (Asset) owner

- For those contributing to the asset beyond the core team
 - Contributing is valuable to the individual contributor at a personal level and an organisation level
 - Sense of putting something back into the community
 - Contribution has potential to be recognised by others

FAIRplus Sustainable Asset Examples

We list some of the core FAIRplus sustainable assets and the plans for their future sustainability.

FAIRplus FAIR Cookbook

One of the key FAIRplus project outputs for sustainability is the [FAIR cookbook](#). The aim of this cookbook was to collate protocols (which we term recipes) for making data FAIR. Recipes include how to FAIRify a number of exemplar data sets, putting the FAIR principles into practice; basic knowledge of what makes data more or less FAIR; understand levels and indicators of FAIRness, and the corresponding maturity model; how to apply the technologies and tools available to assess and improve data FAIRness; learn about user roles and their different perspectives on data, and on the challenges when making data FAIR enough for a specific purpose. The FAIRplus FAIR cookbook was collaboratively developed across the project using agile methodologies, with squads working to scrum schedules, mapping use cases along the 'FAIRification pathway' outlined [here](#):

FAIRplus FAIRification Process

Figure: FAIRplus FAIRification process

With a focus on scalability, maintainability, and hosting we have created deployment workflows. These are executed each time a contribution is sent to the cookbook's content thereby ensuring that output is always in sync with the latest text additions. Over 50 [recipes](#) (Mar 2022) have been developed, consisting of executable code in the form of jupyter notebooks or workflows. Official releases are made and digital identifiers via github and its Zenodo integration.

The cookbook recipes have been extensively tested for completeness and ease of use, and validated on use cases from IMI legacy projects. More on this is available directly within the FAIR cookbook. Similarly, the FAIR Cookbook overall layout, examples and table of contents are used to define the activities of the FAIRplus fellowship programme which kick-starts FAIR activities in data consuming organisations.

For a user, if this doesn't strain a metaphor too far, some thought should be put to whether they're dipping into the cookbook to find something quick for dinner. Or, are they intending something more elaborate and complex, a "metaphoric 5 course meal", in a more involved commitment. Whilst both are possible, continued development of the cookbook beyond the life of the FAIRplus project will necessitate a continued oversight to ensure that recipes have a broader appeal and aren't focused on a narrow community of experts. Both are needed of course, but this cannot become an exercise that benefits one group at the expense of the other. As referenced elsewhere in this whitepaper, there is a continuous need to ensure the community of data experts remains focused both on their own needs of course, but more importantly the needs of the wider scientific data community as a whole. This latter group will contain many without the necessary expertise to grasp and contend with the issues of data FAIRness, but own the vast majority of use cases. A continued emphasis on outreach is an absolute requirement for the data expert community.

In combination with the Dataset maturity model, the Fair Cookbook forms a toolbox for how to foster and deliver change in organisations who want to FAIRify their own data, as well as simplify how they bring data in from the outside world.

FAIRplus Dataset Maturity (DSM) Model

FAIR adoption is very much a journey and a key element of this is understanding the starting point and the stepping stones during the adoption process to better understand how impact and value of FAIR adoption can be activated across the implementation plans.

The [FAIRplus-DSM model](#) is intended as a comprehensive reference model for state-of-FAIRness improvement in research datasets. Based on the FAIR guiding principles, the DSM model defines and classifies requirements that constitute an incremental path towards improving FAIRness level for a given research dataset.

The immediate value of DSM as with Capability Maturity Models in general is to support engagement with FAIR and adoption plans and it's already in use across organisations.

FAIRplus Dataset Maturity Levels

5	Managed Data Assets	Enterprise Level. Data at this level is optimally managed at the most granular level in an environment offering data governance, master data management and reference data management capabilities.
4	Semantically Typed Data	Cross-community Level. This level focuses on cross-domain interoperability and is meant to be the level required for larger harmonization and integration projects.
3	Standardised Data	Community Level. Data at this level complies with community standard domain models, terminologies and formats, and is hosted in an environment offering searching and retrieval capabilities.
2	Described Data	Project Level. All datasets generated within a project are consistently described against a locally defined schema, controlled terminologies, and hosted in an environment offering data catalogue level searching capabilities.
1	Identifiable Data	Data Object level. Data at this level is identifiable as individual generic data objects and described by generic metadata elements. Hosting environment offers limited retrieval capabilities.
0	Single Use Data	No potential for re-use beyond lifetime of the research project

Figure: FAIRplus Dataset Maturity Levels

Having developed this maturity model, hosted on GitHub, the initial key elements of sustain have been met. Where the DSM resource can grow and evolve will for instance be the user implementation stories and best practices that will come from the adoption community over time. This is also the driver for FAIRplus' engagement with the wider stakeholder community e.g. Pistoia Alliance and their FAIR Toolkit.

The value of DSM longer term will heavily rely on the willingness of the community to support description of examples and assessments over the coming years to add to the knowledge base on FAIR adoption and value.

FAIRplus Fellowship programme

Although much attention in FAIR is given to the datasets and workflows themselves, FAIR adoption success will only succeed if training material is available to support new data management scientists ('skilling up') and those experts then support the next wave. The fellowship learning modules have been made publicly available for further reuse. Recipes and training around them in the Fellowship are key dissemination and uptake parameters of the FAIRplus outcomes. The aim of the FAIRplus Fellowship is to highlight the value of this approach but at the moment future support is uncertain beyond the end of the project.

A key goal beyond the current achievements is the incorporation of this material into existing courses and ongoing support for fellowship programmes from funders, institutions and industry.

Ethics and data

A key element of FAIR is the need to consider the ethics and governance of the underlying digital assets including:

- GDPR Principles
- Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)
- Data transfers
- Data actors (DPO, data processor, data controller...)

As well as Ethics project deliverables, some of the output of this work is being incorporated into the FAIRplus Cookbook & Fellowship programme since much is based on the best practices and experiences developed during the project. For instance the development of legal agreements needed to access previous IMI projects' data was a complex and slow process adding months to the point of data access. The ability to have common templates that can accelerate the necessary legal agreements for future projects (as data owners and data accessors) is a key sustainability deliverable. This approach allows the best access levels and continuing support for the ethics needs for FAIR.

Engaging the Community

One of the key challenges for FAIRplus, and indeed any of the various other FAIR programmes and initiatives that are running, is how to engage the wider community beyond data experts in what FAIR is, why it matters, and why they should care. This is a significant challenge to the data community as a whole which is often very introspective. During the FAIRplus project, engagement with the community beyond those involved in the project activities has been an important part of our preparations for sustain. Through consultation with several SMEs and larger companies with little or no awareness of FAIR, it can be challenging to align on why FAIR matters. However on discussion it is relatively easy to establish that one of the FAIR letters is important to an organisation - findability and accessibility have particular resonance for certain use cases while interoperability matters most to others.

This range of awareness of FAIR in the wider community beyond the data community is worth noting. This will be important when FAIRplus sustainability is considered, and the impact of FAIR over the longer term is reviewed. For some organisations, interoperability is fundamental based on key entities that are of interest.

A further factor to consider in FAIRplus sustainability and impact, is the relationship to other FAIR projects and initiatives in the wider data expert community. Whilst there are various seemingly overlapping and competing projects within Europe ([GoFAIR](#), [RDA](#), [Pistoia Alliance](#) etc) there is a certain amount of participant overlap which ensures awareness and alignment at a high level.

Beyond these however, there is an impression that FAIR is a European thing for European people which is of course both as incorrect as it is understandable. For projects that come beyond FAIRplus, a greater emphasis needs to be put on use cases and success stories that reach beyond the immediate data expert field to gain visibility and traction in the wider user community. Greater emphasis needs to be placed on engaging users in the SME world, as well as biopharma academics whose data expertise is generally limited thereby stymying the reach of the data expert community. The results of our informal survey and discussion work with potential users show that FAIR as a whole has some distance to go with the people who arguably can benefit most from its implementation, and future projects really need to take this into consideration from the earliest stages.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Finally, when it comes to sustainability of the outputs of the FAIRplus project, we have to recognise the reality of the challenge in this domain. Sustainability of digital assets³ is complex, expensive, and requires a realistic view on re-use, value drivers and further development in future projects. IHI/IMI (Innovative Health Initiative) in general has a very poor record in sustainability of digital assets precisely because funding issues limit future development (project based vs longer term service) and digital asset uptake. Sustainability may have been a feature of IMI project deliverables, but sustainability cannot just be another box to tick as the services and value needs to be continuously developed to support the user requirements beyond the project timeline. Projects such as [ND4BB Translocation](#) have established an Information Centre to support sustainability longer term. Explicit continuity of some assets is easy to rationally argue, but much tougher to fund as an output of public:private partnerships. Hence the emphasis we put in this white paper on short term sustainability with organisations and projects that exist in the academic sphere, and a call for future IHI projects to implement and develop a longer term sustainability strategy to develop and foster digital assets from across the IMI/IHI project portfolio. Such a call should explicitly explore alignment across the academic and industrial data community to ensure long term sustainability growth of critical data assets with services. FAIR is far more than the technical and data management aspects of FAIR and the need to raise awareness of FAIR among the next generation of researchers is critical. This is another sustainability issue with the current model of support since this requires commitment and funding for the longer term. Equally important is the need to engage with the academic institutes to incorporate key material in future courses. Industry needs to increase its support for FAIR data experts by providing early career experience and progression to reduce its reliance on resource churn from other life sciences organisations.

Stakeholder and policy maker engagement strategy remains critical and will enable a larger impact on FAIR recommendations and FAIRplus [D4.4](#) (FAIRplus Policy Maker Engagement Strategy) highlights some key actions. We recommend stronger alignment between EFPIA Project Asset Continuity teams, IMI ops and EFPIA sustainability taskforce and other industry groups. The aim would be to create more visibility for FAIR implementation tools, help underscore SOPs, best practices and recommendations to funding bodies and policy makers and bring a stronger FAIR voice to the table.

³ Frontiers | Getting Digital Assets from Public–Private Partnership Research Projects through “The Valley of Death,” and Making Them Sustainable | Medicine <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2018.00065>

This requires some significant political changes, but also a realisation that the Private Public Partnership (PPP) flavour of IHI/IMI is its biggest advantage. However this is an advantage that significantly complicates future funding decisions if these are not aligned with larger projects and initiatives in the public domain. In order to really sustain and develop project output, it is vital for EFPIA companies to continue to engage and fund sustainability of the assets they have created through IMI. Currently, EFPIA funding is very low to non-existent. There are few success stories, and those assets that do continue to evolve and progress face severe funding issues.

Whilst IHI/IMI and EFPIA put a lot of emphasis on SMEs picking up digital assets as a future business model, experience shows that this underestimates the funding really needed for sustain and success, and also has a very unrealistic high expectation of customer numbers. The reality is that the costs of sustaining these digital assets far exceeds any revenue that is generated, and with these clear economic disincentives it is far from surprising that sustaining digital assets is very unattractive to SMEs from a business perspective. Similarly, it pits SMEs into direct competition with public data infrastructure rather than their natural focus on value-added services and analytics.

To fully realise sustainable IHI/IMI digital assets, both IHI/IMI and EFPIA need a far more realistic view of the funding issues involved, and should seek alignment with EU and national funders for valuable digital assets to be sustained in partnership with the wider community through explicitly funded programmes as part of ELIXIR infrastructures and services. Alternatively, IHI/IMI and EFPIA should explore positioning valuable digital assets as part of EOSC. In both cases, mechanisms to transfer ownership and responsibility to an appropriate academic infrastructure will be key to ensuring that future growth and development can be incorporated in future funded projects. As an example, the adoption of the FAIR cookbook recipes within EFPIA members and the relevant feedback on how to improve the recipes will be a key element of future success and impact. Without this feedback and future updates the recipes will be unable to reflect the real world needs of the community.

IHI/IMI as a vehicle for high value PPPs producing valuable basic research and clinical insights is unparalleled. It is unfortunate indeed that much of the data and digital assets created through multiple programmes are at risk of being lost to the very communities that need it. The digital legacy of IHI/IMI can be rescued if we act creatively now, but time is of the essence.

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Author Information

Affiliations

Bryn Williams-Jones - OpenPHACTS Foundation

Nick Lynch- [Curlew Research](#) & [OpenPHACTS Foundation](#)